

SPIN TESTS OF DISK MADE OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THREE-DIMENSIONAL COMPOSITE

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D_i	: Inner diameter
D_o	: Outer diameter
D_r	: $D_r = D_i/D_o$
D_h	: Height diameter
V_t	: Volume function of total
V_r	: Fiber volume function in r direction
V_θ	: Volume function in θ direction
V_z	: Volume function of z direction
v_{t-max}	: Maximum tip speed

1. Introduction

In recent years, on the basis of demands for hybrid and electric cars, various energy conservation techniques have been developed. Nickel-metal hydride batteries are used in a typical hybrid car, lithium-ion batteries are expected to be replaced in near future. However, such chemical batteries possess a common problem that energy densities capable of in- and outputting is small. This problem is derived from the fact that when energy is rapidly saved in the chemical battery, a significant part of energy is dissipated as heat, and cannot be saved as regenerative energy.

Compared to chemical batteries, flywheel battery has advantages of lightweight, pollution-free, large in and output energy densities and long life. Total energy that can be stored in a flywheel is proportional to the mass, proportional to the square of the angular velocity and radius (square of tip speed of disk). The maximum stress induced in a rotating disk is proportional to the square of the

angular velocity and radius. Therefore, in order to store high energy density (per unit weight or volume), a material with low density and high strength (high specific strength) is highly required to withstand the strong centrifugal force during high-speed rotation of a flywheel disk. Thus, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) have been examined as a candidate material for high energy density flywheel disks [1].

In general, the tensile stresses in the radial and circumferential directions are induced in a rotating disk, and the stress in the circumferential direction is particularly high. Thus, unidirectionally reinforced CFRP disks (UD-disk) placing the fibers only in the circumferential direction were mainly studied [2]. However, UD-disks have been fractured at a premature rotation speed due to delaminations parallel to the fibers caused by low strength of the interface between the metal hub and the CFRP disk and/or low tensile strength of the unidirectionally reinforced CFRP in the direction normal to the fibers [2]. In other words, the UD-disks do not take full advantage of the characteristics of CFRP, high tensile strength in the fiber direction.

Multi-ring discs have been studied to reduce the radial stress [3-5], and to increase a CFRP portion. The multi-ring disk is composed of plural concentric rings, circumferentially fiber-wound, to which compressive forces have been induced in the radial direction in advance by a tight fit of the rings. In previous studies, the radius ration ($D_r =$

D_i/D_o) was reduced to 0.6 by adopting multi-ring method, and a maximum tip speed of 1,000m /s was attained.

To improve further the maximum tip speed and to increase favorable CFRP portion, reinforcing radial direction by fibers is likely required. The purpose of this study is to examine potential of three-dimensionally carbon-fiber-reinforced (3D-CFRP) disks for a high-speed rotating, in which fibers are placed in the circumferential, radial, and thickness directions, and to achieve a maximum burst tip speed higher than existing disks.

This paper reports the current state of our development of a 3D-CFRP disk, i.e., optimally and 3-dimensionally designed fiber arrangement, processing into CFRP using the 3D-weaved preform, and rotation tests using the resultant disk.

The designed annual 3D-CFRP disks have small inner diameter. Hence, a disk rotate at a high speed, the inner wall of the disk tends to detach from the outer radius (D_h) wall of a metal hub due to high centrifugal force acting to the disk. The clearance thus formed is likely to induce vibration of the disk. In this study, we examined several techniques to suppress the clearance between D_h and D_i .

2 Analysis

To demonstrate that the 3D-CFRP disks have a potential to sustain a higher rotation speed compared with UD-CFRP disks, burst tip speeds of various disks were numerically estimated using a commercial finite element cord, ABAQUS 6.6.2.1

2.1 Boundary condition

Modeled 3D-CFRP disks are reinforced in the r , θ , and z directions. Thus, they have orthotropic properties with nine independent values. The elastic properties and strengths of the 3D-CFRP disks were estimated using the equivalent inclusion method. High strength type PAN-based-carbon-fiber (TORAYCA T1000G, Toray, Japan) was assumed in the calculations. Table 1 shows physical properties of the matrix and reinforcing fiber used

in the calculations. Total fiber volume fraction V_t of three-dimensionally reinforced fabric is calculated to be 58% under geometric assumption that the three axes have the same fiber volume fraction. Calculations were carried out repeatedly so as to maximize fracture rotation speed under the following conditions changing the V_{θ} and $V_{r\theta}$.

(1) $V_{r\theta}$ is 5%.

(2) The sum of $V_{r\theta}$ and V_{θ} is 50%.

In this study, D_o was assumed to be 300mm, the height along the inner radius 20mm, and inner/outer diameter ration D_r was varied by changing D_i . Two types of 3D-CFRP disks were examined. The first model (3D-CFRP-A) has a constant thickness of 20mm. The second disk (3D-CFRP-B) has variable thickness, which was determined so as to minimize stress/strength ratios. For attaining high strength, the continuity of reinforcing fiber is imperative. In order to satisfy this condition, all disks were assumed to have constant number of fiber bundles in the radial direction. Thus, the $V_{r\theta}$ of the 3D-CF-A is inversely proportional to r . Once $V_{r\theta}$ is fixed at inner radius, V_{θ} is automatically determined from condition (2). Since the thickness of 3D-CF-B was varied in the fashion inversely proportional to r , $V_{r\theta}$ is near constant. Hence, from the condition of (2), V_{θ} was also set to almost constant. The hub connecting a disk and shaft was assumed to be made of Ti (Ti-6Al-4V), because specific strength of Ti is stronger than other metals. Table 2 lists physical properties of titanium.

For the purpose of comparison, the burst tip speeds of two types of conventional disks were also evaluated. The first is unidirectionally reinforced composite disk, in which carbon fiber is wound only in the circumferential direction (UD-CFs). The second is a multi-ring system (MR-CFs), produced by press-fit of rings. The $V_{f\theta}$ s of the UD-CFs and MR-CFs were assumed to be 60% [4-6]. Figures 1 and 2 show axisymmetric models for finite element analysis of 3D-CF-B and 3D-CF-A.

These finite element models are equally divided into 40 axisymmetric elements in the radial span. Material properties unique to its radial position were assigned to each element. The physical properties of each element were calculated from V_{JR} and $V_{J\theta}$ defined by the position of r . Burst tip speed (v_{t-max}) was evaluated using the maximum stress criterion, wherein fracture was assumed to occur when stress reached 75 % of the tensile strength of the composite.

Table 1 Physical properties of the matrix and fiber

	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Density [g/cm ³]	Poisson's ratio
T1000 G	6370	297	1.8	0.31
Epoxy resin	100	3.4	1.25	0.35

Table 2 Physical properties of the titanium

	Proof strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Density [g/cm ³]	Poisson's ratio
Ti-6Al-4V	800	112	4.5	0.3

Figure 1 Axisymmetric representation of finite element model for the 3D-CF-A.

Figure 2 Axisymmetric representation of finite element model for the 3D-CF-B.

2.2 Analytical results

Figure 3 shows calculation results of v_{t-max} for the composite disks and Ti-hub as a function of D_r . It follows from this figure that introduction of the 3D-CF-B improves v_{t-max} significantly compared with the UD-CF and MR-CF. In general, circumferential tensile stress σ_θ increases with increasing D_r , and radial tensile stress σ_r increases with decreasing D_r .

Therefore, when diameter ratio becomes small, the tensile strength in the r direction of the UD-CF tends to be insufficient, and the maximum tip speed becomes lower. Thus, the UD-CF is advantageous only when D_r is larger than 0.9. The MR-CF improves this shortcoming in the range around $D_r=0.5$ to 0.8, and enhance burst tip speed up to about 1,000m/s [4~6].

In Figure 3, the burst tip speed v_{t-max} of the 3D-CF-A is predicted to drop when D_r is smaller than 0.4. On the other hand, the v_{t-max} of the 3D-CF-B is enhanced when D_r becomes even smaller than 0.2. This behavior is due to high thickness of the 3D-CF-B at near center of the disk. The thick inner region sustains the load by high centrifugal force transferred from outer region. It should be noted in Figure 3 that a v_{t-max} of 1,700m/s is predicted for the 3D-CF-B, and this is higher than that of any existing rotors.

Next, let us discuss v_{t-max} taking the fracture of the Ti-hub into account. In Figure 3, the intersection of two curves of a composite disk and the Ti-hub indicates that the fracture occurs simultaneously in both of them. The three intersection points of the Ti-hub and the composites, UD-CF, 3D-CF-A, and 3D-CF-B, are at D_r equal to 0.78, 0.55, and 0.45, respectively. When D_r is larger than these values, the Ti-hub fracture should occur before composite fracture. Hence, fracture of Ti-hub is likely suppressed when the MR-CF disk is used compared with the UD-CF having the same value of D_r . However, when the 3D-CF-B is adopted, the

fracture of Ti-hub can be prevented in a wide range of D_r .

Figure 3 Burst tip speed (v_{t-max}) of composite disks and Ti-hub as a function of D_r .

3 Design of 3D-CFRP-rotor-system

3.1 Disk design

It was found by the finite element calculations that the 3D-CF-B disk having D_r less than 0.45 has a v_{t-max} of more than 1,500m/s. Prototype rotors were designed and fabricated based on this result. The configuration of the prototype 3D-CFRP disks is shown in Figure 4. This disk has an outer diameter of 305mm and inner diameter of 42mm; D_r is 0.14. The thicknesses at several radii of the disks were set following the optimum condition determined by the calculations; namely $t=12$ mm at $r=35.6$ mm, $t=6.3$ mm at $r=78.6$ mm, and $t=4$ mm at the outer radius, and linearly connecting these thickness along the in-between radii. The inner most part between $r=21$ and 35.6mm was inversely tapered in order to couple the disk with the Ti-hub. In accordance with this design, 3D fabrics supplied from SIKIBO Inc., Japan were fabricated for the prototype rotor using the high strength type PAN-based carbon fiber (TORAYCA T1000G, Toray Japan). In order to endure high-speed rotation, reinforcing fiber must be stretched continuously

from inner to outer radius as shown in Figure 5. The resulting average volume fraction of fibers in the formed fabrics were $V_{fR}=16.6\%$, $V_{f\theta}=26.2\%$, $V_{fZ}=2.6\%$, and $V_f=45.4\%$, comparing with the optimally designed values of $V_{fR}=18.3\%$, $V_{f\theta}=25.2\%$, $V_{fZ}=2.4\%$, and $V_f=45.9\%$.

Figure 4 Shape and dimensions of the prototype 3D-CFRP disk.

Figure 5 Schematic of the fiber orientation in the 3D fabric for the prototype rotor.

3.2 Disk/hub interface

When a hub and a disk rotate independently, the displacement at the inner radius of the disk D_i exceeds that at the outer radius of the metal hub D_h . Accordingly, in order to secure joining of the disk and hub, some mechanism is required to avoid separation of the two parts and inducing vibration. In this study, a mechanism using a tapered ring thrusting upward by means of a disk spring was adopted to maintain the contact and to pressurize on the interface between the 3D-CFRP disk and hub.

Figure 6 illustrates the mechanism joining the hub and a disk.

Figure 6 Assembly of the rotor system illustrating mechanism supporting the disk using tapered ring

4 Composite forming processes

4.1 Resin infiltration

Three 3D-CF-B disks were fabricated taking an advantage of potential allowing high speed rotation. A three-dimensional fabric for 3D-CF-B was impregnated with cyanate ester resin (EX-1545, TENCATE, Company) by the resin transfer molding (RTM). The cyanate ester resin was employed as the matrix because of its high fluidity and good wettability to the carbon fiber. In orthogonal three-dimensionally-woven fabrics, closed spaces called the matrix pockets are present at the intersection of orthogonal fiber bundles, and it is hard to completely fill liquid resin in them even when the resin has low viscosity. Therefore, trial impregnations were conducted directly observing resin flow, and resin impregnation conditions to minimize insufficient impregnation were at first determined.

4.2 Flow visualization

Figure 7 shows experimental setup for flow visualization of resin infiltration process. The resin flows from the reserver (left) to the mold (center)

made of acrylic plates for easy observation of resin flow in the mold and finally to the trap tank (right). Figure 8 shows a cross-section of the mold illustrating the sealing method and procedure to inject the resin in the mold (RTM process). In this experiment, the resin warmed to 60°C was injected into the mold evacuated higher than 0.1 atm from the inlet located at the bottom. Resin flowed upwardly while impregnating the fabric in the mold, and excess resin was drained from the outlet located at the mold top.

The result of the first infiltration test was shown in Figure 9. In this run, the resin reached the outlet only ten seconds after starting resin flow mainly through a clearance between the outer periphery of the fabric and the mold wall. Then, at a passage time of 170 seconds, the resin covered all the macroscopic spaces in the mold, but leaving large voids as shown in the black area in the 2nd and 3rd photos. The resin was still flown after $t = 170s$, but the voids could not be eliminated completely. Figure 10 shows a photograph of the surface of the disk taken after curing the resin. It is understood from this figure that many voids remained in the resulting composite at the voided place in the resin infiltration process.

Figure 11 shows the infiltration process of the fifth visualization test. In this run, the reduced pressure in the mold was alleviated to 0.6 atm, and the clearance between the mold and a fabric was minimized using tight spacers. These conditions were set to minimize resin flow through the clearance and to allowing slow infiltration, in which the horizontal flow front was maintained until infiltration completed. As shown in Figure 11, this condition was satisfied, and thus trapping voids were minimized. Infiltrations of 3D fabrics for rotation disks were performed using the conditions of Figure 11. Figure 12 shows photographs on a surface of the disk in the fifth run. It was found that voids were significantly suppressed compared to the case in Figure 10.

Figure 7 Experimental setup for flow visualization of the resin infiltration process. The resin flows from the reservoir (left) to the mold (center) and finally to the trap tank (right).

Figure 8 Cross-sectional view of the sealing system adopted in the mold for the resin flow visualization.

Figure. 9 Visualized infiltration process under a molding pressure of 0.1 atm.

Figure 10 Surface of 3D fabric resin-infiltrated at 0.1 atm. Large voids were formed at the first run.

Figure 11 Visualized infiltration process at molding pressure at 0.6 atm.

Figure 12 Surface of resin-infiltrated fabric at 0.6 atm. Voids were almost suppressed.

5. Spin tests using 3D-CFRP prototype-rotor

After the resin infiltration and curing of the matrix resin, a 3D-CFRP prototype-rotor was assembled as shown in Figure 13. The prototype rotor was machined into an outer diameter of 305mm, height of 150mm and weight of 1.8kg. A high-speed rotation test was conducted to evaluate the performance of the prototype rotor using a spin tester (Maruwa Electronic Inc., Japan) driven by air turbines. Figure 14 shows overview of the spin

tester. The pressure in the test chamber in which the prototype rotor was set was reduced to 80Pa to avoid explosion when CFRP fractures, and a high-speed rotation test was performed at a rotational acceleration of 100rpm / s.

An eddy current sensor (Denshioyo Inc., japan) was installed near the rotor shaft to observe shaft vibration.

Figure 15 shows relation between the rotation speed and amplitude of shaft vibration during the spin test. The spin test was discontinued at 557m/s before reaching the target speed of 1500m/s because of vibration grew.

Figure. 13 Outlook of the 3D-CFRP prototype rotor.

Figure 14 Overview of the spintester.

Figure 15 Rotation speed and shaft vibration as a function of time.

6 Vibration analysis

6.1 Fourier- transform

Spin test data was analyzed to find a source of the vibration increase to be made the rotation test terminate. Figure 16 shows the Fourier-transformed intensities depending on rotation speed and frequency. Two types of the intensity are observed. The first one is synchronized with the rotational speed, and the other is not synchronized but at constant frequency. It follows from this figure that the vibration at the high frequency range is related to the synchronized component. It is well known that synchronous component is induced by forced vibration along with the imbalance in the rotational body.

Figure.16Vibrational spectra of each rotational speed

7. Discussions

The increase in unbalance can be considered as the main cause of vibration growth that is synchronized with the rotation speed.

Fig.12 is composed of several parts that have a possibility to infinitesimally slip on component's interfaces. These slips seem to have a strong potential for the changing of the rotational balance. Among them, slips on the interface between the upper surface of the 3D-CFRP disk and the metal hub can be considered as a most plausible candidate because of the disk 's relatively strong susceptibility to centrifugal force.

Unlike metal alloy, CFRP is heterogeneous due to random nature of the mixing of the fibers and matrix resin. Before testing, dynamic imbalance was fixed within 0.15 (gmm) when the rotor system was finally assembled. However, if small slip occurs during rotation, even small rotational imbalance embedded in the CFRP disk might

facilitate growth of the imbalance of the rotor assembly.

To evaluate the effect of the slip and increasing imbalance, FEM calculation using ABACUS 6.6 was conducted on the model composed of three parts, the disk, hub and tapered ring. In the model, friction elements were inserted between on the interface between the disk and hub. Embedded imbalance in the CFRP disk induced by heterogeneity is assumed to be 0.15 (g · mm) and is positioned at the outer edge of disk.

Fig.17 shows normal radial stress distribution in MPa including radial deformation at the tip speed of 638 m/s (40000rpm). In this figure, the right hand side of inner radius is not in contact with the hub. This deviation from the center of the CFRP disk can be considered to cause the vibration increase.

Figure 17 Analytical result simulating generation of clearance between the disk and hub resulting in additional rotation imbalance.

8. Future scope

In order to eliminate slippage of the disk and vibration increase, a new disk was designed as shown in Fig. 18. This disk can maintain constant contact of the disk with the hub by bending deformation of an area near the inner diameter during high-speed rotation. Figure 19

shows analysis results by ABAQUS 6.6. In this figure, it is confirmed that the hub is compressed at the target rotation speed.

Figure 18 Illustration of the new model.

Figure 19 Normal stress distribution in the radial direction around the joining interface between the disk and hub of the new model.

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